

WAYS OF FORMATION OF NEOLOGISMS IN THE TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES OF THE MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7943812>

Annotation: The main goal of this work is the theoretical and practical study of neologisms in the terminological system of computer technologies of the modern English language. In this regard, the terminological system in the field of computer technology is becoming more open and accessible to modern society.

Key words: lexeme, conversion, compound words, mass media, Internet communications, semantic derivation.

Today we can observe the rapid and rapid development of computer technology. This is the main reason for the appearance of new words in the computer sublanguage. Due to the fact that every year more and more new vocabulary appears, it is advisable to streamline and systematize it. Computerization is currently taking place not only in all spheres of science, but also its penetration into the everyday life of modern people. Hardly any other area of human life is developing so dynamically and is able to compete with the field of computer technology in terms of the emergence of new realities that need to be identified. It is quite difficult to imagine a modern person who does not have basic knowledge in the field of computer technology.

The English language has undergone a long evolution from the ancient Anglo-Saxon language to its current state and continues to change at the present time. Migration to the British Isles, Viking raids, the Norman Conquest, the end of the Hundred Years War, great geographical discoveries, subsequent revolutions in science and society, the development of information technology, the adoption of new pronunciation standards, the introduction of new lexical units and the semantic transformation of old words brought new features and characteristics to English in general and its vocabulary in particular. The key point in the development of any spoken language is the continuous enrichment and expansion of its vocabulary. Newly formed or borrowed words, known as neologisms, after a certain period of perception as unusual and new, then enter the stock of an established lexicon or even an encyclopedic dictionary as an integral part of it.[1]

Therefore, the lexicological layer seems to be the first reliable indicator of gradual and continuous linguistic transformation and development. But it is lexical innovations that make changes in the language so noticeable, obvious and indisputable. The purpose of this article is to consider the formation of neologisms that have been used in the English lexicon for a long period of time and therefore have already acquired a certain official status, and, therefore, have entered or are in the process of being included in the official English language.

To solve the tasks, the following research methods were used:

- method of continuous scanning of lexicographic sources;
- method of comparison of definitions;
- sociolinguistic method of correlation of linguistic and social phenomena;

- statistical method of quantitative and percentage characteristics; as well as structural-semantic analysis.[2]

So, in order for a language to fully fulfill its main function - the function of a means of communication, its vocabulary must quickly respond to changes occurring in all spheres of people's lives and activities: in production, science, culture, socio-economic relations - and fix them. The complication of the forms of social life, the development and deepening of the entire sum of human knowledge of the surrounding reality causes the emergence of new words and the gradual displacement from the linguistic use of those words that were associated with the past stage of social practice and ideology.

The introduction of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language is available to every teacher, it is important that the study of the material would interest children, make them think that they need a foreign language, if not in their future profession, then just to feel like an educated person. The use of modern educational technologies helps to increase motivation, interest in the subject, the desire to learn the language and communicate in it. It is important to distinguish between IT literacy and IT competence of a teacher.

It is likely that some educators may create their own learning materials for the virtual learning space. But, as a rule, when it comes to choosing a virtual learning environment, determining an adequate share of web presence in this learning space, which corresponds to a certain target group, as well as compiling meaningfully adequate online materials, then a team of specialists' works on these tasks. When developing an online course, the teacher is not autonomous, as when introducing a new course in the classroom. [3]

Neologisms are used in all spheres of human life, especially in the field of psychology and communications. Moreover, this fact takes place both in Russian and in English. This proves that the emergence of neologisms is an integral process of language development. The use of new words should not be avoided: it is impossible and meaningless. They need to be studied. The use of neologisms contributes to the expansion of vocabulary, understanding of modern life. [4]

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